

had been mixed with fertilizer N during soil incorporation was retained as seed for further multiplication. In monocrop and intercrop plots, fresh azolla was inoculated. Adverse effects of more than 50 kg N/ha would be reduced by minimizing mixing of fertilizer N and azolla or by seeding fresh azolla for further multiplication.

The poor response of azolla to applied P may be due to the high available P in the soil and its increased availability under flooded conditions.

Monocropping for 20 d and dual cropping for 50 d resulted in higher yields of fresh azolla, contributing more N/day, dry matter content, and K

Table 2. Effect of N and cultivation method interaction on yield of fresh azolla, Bangalore, India, 1983 wet season.

N (kg/ha)	Total yield of fresh azolla (t/ha)			
	Monocropping	Intercropping	Dual cropping	Mean
0	21.0	16.0	37.8	24.9
50	19.8	15.4	37.1	24.1
100	18.5	15.6	31.5	21.8
Mean	19.8	15.6	35.4	23.6
LSD (P=0.05)	2.4 ^a	3.0 ^b		

^aBetween 2 methods of cultivation at same level of N. ^bBetween 2 N levels in same cultivation method.

content of dry matter. Monocrop azolla did not experience any competition with rice. Intercrop azolla suffered

considerable competition with rice for all growth factors, in particular light and nutrients. □

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of seedling age and leaf removal on rice grain and straw yields

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We studied the effect of age of seedling and removal of leaf on rice grain and straw yields during kharif 1988, at the Seed Farm (23.5° N, 89.0° E, and 9.75 mean sea level). Treatments were three seedling ages and four leaf removal levels, in a split-plot design with four replications.

Soil was clayey loam (0.61% organic C, 0.59% total N, 14 kg available P/ha, 208 kg available K/ha, and pH 6.8). Fertilizer was 40-50-50 kg NPK/ha

applied at plowing and 50 kg N/ha applied 30 d after transplanting (DT). IR8 seedlings at 21, 28, and 35 d after seeding were transplanted 20 Jul at 25-×

15-cm spacing, four seedlings/hill. Leaves were removed (0, 25, 50, and 100%) 1 mo after transplanting in 7.5-× 2.0-m subplots.

Seedling age did not significantly affect grain and straw yields. Grain and straw yields decreased with increased leaf removal (see table). □

Effect of seedling age and leaf removal on rice grain and straw yields of IR8. West Bengal, India, 1988.

Seedling age (d)	Yield (t/ha)									
	No leaves removed		25% of leaves removed		50% of leaves removed		100% of leaves removed		Mean	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
21	4.8	5.0	3.6	4.0	3.6	4.0	2.8	3.6	3.7	4.1
28	4.4	4.7	4.4	5.0	4.0	4.5	3.8	4.7	4.2	4.7
35	4.5	4.9	3.7	4.2	3.2	3.5	3.1	3.3	3.6	4.0
Mean	4.6	4.8	3.9	4.4	3.6	4.0	3.2	3.9	—	—
LSD (0.05)										
Leaf removal		0.7	grain	0.7	straw					

Influence of potassium and kinetin on protein partitioning in rice

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We examined protein partitioning in rice, using short-duration Triveni in a summer 1987 field experiment at Karamana (8.5° N, 77.9° E, and 29 m above sea level). Soil of the experimental field was sandy loam, pH 4.5, with 84.3, 13.6, 63.8 ppm available NPK.

Treatments, a factorial combination of four potassium levels (0, 14.5, 29.1, 58.1) and four kinetin spray treatments, are given in Table 1. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

K as KCl was applied 50% basal and 50% at panicle initiation; 70 kg N and

15.4 kg P/ha were applied uniformly. The crop was raised following the KAU package of recommended practices.

Protein contents of leaf, sheath, culm, and panicle were analyzed by the improved Kjeldahl method ($N \times 6.25$). Protein yield was worked out by multiplying protein content of a sample by sample dry weight, expressed in kg/ha. Protein content in source and sink was also worked out as percentage of total protein produced (Table 1, 2).

Protein content in leaf, sheath, and culm decreased with increased K up to

29.1 kg K/ha (Table 1). Protein yield increased with K level, a 106% increase in plants treated with 58 kg K/ha.

Plants treated with 58 kg K/ha contained 71.6% of the total protein in the sink.

In general, protein content of source (leaf, sheath, or culm) decreased with kinetin spray, with a corresponding increase in grain protein content. Two sprays of kinetin resulted in accumulation of the highest amount of protein in the grain (9.37%). Protein yield also increased with kinetin spray.

The sink of plants treated with two sprays of kinetin contained 507 kg protein/ha, 71% of total protein.

There was a significant negative correlation between grain yield and protein content of leaf (-0.72**), sheath (-0.81**), and culm (-0.39**); there was a significant positive correlation between grain yield and protein content of panicle (0.91**).

The K-kinetin interaction was significant on protein content of leaf, sheath, and panicle, and synergistic on grain protein and total protein yield (Table 2). Application of 29.1 kg K/ha with two sprays of kinetin resulted in the highest accumulation of protein in the sink (73.6%). These results indicate a synergistic $K \times$ kinetin interaction to mobilize protein from source to sink. □

Table 1. Influence of K and kinetin on protein content and protein yield of different plant parts. Trivandrum, India, 1987 summer.

Treatment	Protein content at harvest (%)				Protein yield at harvest (kg/ha)		Percentage of total protein in	
	Leaf	Sheath	Culm	Panicle	Panicle	Total	Source	Sink
No K	3.62	3.73	4.06	6.65	250.6	418.9	40.2	59.8
14.5 kg K/ha	3.47	3.60	4.01	8.40	405.5	596.0	32.0	68.0
29.1 kg K/ha	3.22	3.53	3.95	8.96	469.7	667.5	29.6	70.4
58.1 kg K/ha	3.23	3.54	3.91	9.55	517.8	723.0	28.4	71.6
Water spray	3.49	3.64	3.97	7.52	318.1	489.2	35.0	65.0
10 ppm kinetin at flowering	3.41	3.61	4.02	8.02	372.1	554.3	32.9	67.1
10 ppm kinetin at 10 d after flowering (DF)	3.33	3.59	3.99	8.65	445.9	647.8	31.2	68.8
10 ppm kinetin at flowering and at 10 DF	3.32	3.54	3.95	9.37	507.4	714.2	29.0	71.0
LSD (0.05)	0.11	0.04	ns	0.24	27.9	39.2	-	-

Table 2. Potassium \times kinetin interaction on protein content and protein yield of different plant parts. Trivandrum, India, 1987 summer.

Treatment combination	Protein content at harvest (%)				Protein yield at harvest (kg/ha)		Percentage of total protein in	
	Leaf	Sheath	Culm	Panicle	Panicle	Total	Source	Sink
No K + water spray	3.69	3.78	4.08	5.73	166.9	307.4	45.7	54.3
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering	3.55	3.78	4.07	6.07	186.3	330.7	43.7	56.3
+ 10 ppm kinetin at 10 d after flowering (DF)	3.56	3.75	4.04	6.54	262.6	451.1	41.8	56.2
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering and at 10 DF	3.66	3.59	4.05	8.26	386.5	586.3	34.1	65.9
14.5 kg K/ha + water spray	3.56	3.63	4.08	7.14	290.1	473.4	38.7	61.3
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering	3.59	3.68	4.04	8.13	360.1	540.5	33.4	66.6
+ 10 ppm kinetin at 10 DF	3.43	3.57	4.01	8.56	419.8	612.2	31.4	68.6
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering and at 10 DF	3.31	3.53	3.92	9.76	552.1	757.9	27.1	72.9
29.1 kg K/ha + water spray	3.44	3.61	4.04	7.89	358.3	538.6	33.5	66.5
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering	3.34	3.49	4.03	8.12	390.1	581.0	32.9	67.1
+ 10 ppm kinetin at 10 DF	3.15	3.55	3.93	9.80	544.8	754.9	27.8	72.2
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering and at 10 DF	2.96	3.45	3.80	10.02	585.4	795.6	26.4	73.6
58.1 kg K/ha + water spray	3.26	3.55	3.69	9.33	456.8	637.5	28.3	71.7
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering	3.16	3.48	3.95	9.76	552.1	764.8	27.8	72.2
+ 10 ppm kinetin at 10 DF	3.16	3.52	3.98	9.68	556.5	772.9	28.0	72.0
+ 10 ppm kinetin at flowering and at 10 DF	3.35	3.61	4.01	9.44	505.7	716.9	29.5	70.5
LSD (0.05)	0.21	0.08	ns	0.48	55.7	78.4		

Effect of plant growth regulators on ripening, grain development, and rice quality

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We studied the effect of plant growth regulators in a pot experiment laid out in a completely randomized block design with four replications.

IR6 seedlings were transplanted at 30 d after seeding, 3 seedlings/240-mm-diameter, 300-mm-deep pot. An aqueous solution of 100 ppm gibberellic acid (GA_3) and 100 ppm indoleacetic acid (IAA) were sprayed at 3 ml/plant at panicle initiation.

Application of growth regulators at panicle initiation significantly affected plant height, tillers/plant, grains/panicle, 1,000-grain weight, sterility, abortive kernels, grain yield, and protein content (see table). Higher, better quality yield with GA_3 and IAA may be the result of more efficient, vigorous leaves and other plant parts for a longer period because of delayed senescence in treated plants. □